

TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH ERNEST HEMINGWAY'S NOVELS AND ITS SYMBOL FOR B2 LEVEL LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the study is to gain knowledge regarding how a number of teachers approach the teaching of symbolism in Ernest Hemingway's writing in upper-level learners in Uzbekistan and share different methods of teaching it. The focus is on how they view the role of literature on how they incorporate it. By exploring such matters, successful approaches can be identified as well as potential difficulties, which may be of use in the development of efficient teaching practices.

INTRODUCTION

In our country, there is also education system which is that during the process of learning English students learn English and American literature especially, educators. That is because that it is in literature that true life can be found and it is under the mask of fiction that you can tell the truth. Therefore, literature is included in the education system. The first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov said " Education and science, is the capital, which

creates a solid foundation for the formation of the country's highly intellectual society that holds the future".

Learning literature also assumes that the ways in which students learn and think are deeply influenced by cultural identity and heritage, and that to teach Ernest Hemingway's novels requires educational approaches that value and recognize American cultural backgrounds. In this way, teaching-learning literature aims to improve the learning and success of all

students, particularly, in learning literature. By exploring such matters, successful approaches can be identified as well as potential difficulties, which may be of use in the development of efficient teaching practices. More specifically, the following research questions will be addressed :

How do some English teachers approach literature for B2 level learners?

What are these teachers' ideals when it comes to working with literature in English class?

What are some common difficulties experienced by these teachers when working with Ernest Hemingway's works in English class?

II BACKGROUND KNOWLEDGE

One of the greatest authors is Ernest Hemingway. Ernest Hemingway is the most famous writer of America. According to Pickering and Hoepfer (1981:649) that the creation of literature can born from uniquely human activity; it showed on man's timeless desire to understand, express, and finally share experiences. A style of the writer should be using words simple and direct, personal, and imagery rich. The greatest writers have the gift of brilliant ideas, are competent stylists. High (2000:147) found "Hemingway's style is usually short and simple, and rarely using adjective but sometimes using repeat short story. Hemingway likes creating novels that follow a chronological order and a "typical" of great American author. He uses symbols, image verbalization and reality in his works. His writing is the most recognizable and prestigious prose of the twentieth century. There are so many novels in which he has used symbolism. He has a close relation with the word "symbol". Symbols overlook existence of Ernest Hemingway's

characters. His technique is unproblematic with simple grammar and easily approachable language. His authentication is in clean way. He does not focus on reflection but action. The powerful impact of Hemingway's writing on other writers remains to this day. The researcher must focus on symbolism and use symbolic element in literary writing. Ernest Hemingway is allotted a significant place among the famous writers. Through symbolism, he makes the world around the pair waiting from the train and evolves the apparently trivial contest between them into a fight against human situation. Symbols in Hemingway's stories differ from brilliance to the apparently minuscule. He fills his story with mixture of symbols that help the portray the whole matter of the story. Works of literature can lead us to see profoundly into and beyond things through the use of symbols which are generally actions, characters or even objects. The features of a symbol are connected to the abstractions it comprises. A thought connect to a field of worry in the work can be a symbol. The meaning and image of symbol express far more than mere words. Ernest Hemingway examines this by his effective use of symbolism in his works to search the disillusionment and the determination of individuals against the background of a pitiless environment.

His style of writing involves getting right to the core of the scene without spending much time on building of characters. He uses declarative language. But this unique style of writing made many feel that Hemingway is an artist in his essence. His writings are regarded more contributed with a power to arouse higher levels of

emotions and that would be because of his real life experiences.

Hemingway did not like discussions regarding the symbolism in his famous works. Fraser Drew said about: "No good writer ever prepared his symbols ahead of time and wrote his book about them, but out of a good book which is true to life symbols may arise and be profitably explored if not over-emphasized."

III METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

The present theory is focused on analyzing how Ernest Hemingway's novels and its symbols are being taught in the B2 level learners at the university and suggesting the most effective teaching methods of literature by making experiments. In the current research work the researcher is determined on studying the impact of different teaching and learning methods and games on B2 level group and find out whether these methods and comprehensive games can be accepted as an effective way of teaching and learning literature. For this The lecture group:

reason the researcher has studied several research papers and articles relevant to the topic, literature on methodology and articles dedicated to teaching literature and analyzing Ernest Hemingway's novels and its symbols. In order to check the impact of different methods and approaches on upper-level students the researcher supposes to conduct an experiment with two participant groups.

B. Participants

The researcher has chosen for this paper the two groups. The reason they were chosen is that those students are zeal, industrious, sociable and therefore they are considered as appropriate subjects to have this experiment. The first group consists of 8 students, 2 of them are male and 6 of them are female. Almost everyone in this class is in the same age and the same nation – Uzbek. The second group consists of 8 students, one of them is male and others are female. Almost every student is in the same age and the nation- Uzbek.

The lecture group:

Group№	Age	Gender		Total number N=8
		Male	Female	
Group -1	22-24	2	6	8

The seminar group:

Group№	Age	Gender		Total number N=8
		Male	Female	

Group№2	20-22	1	7	8
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C. Instruments

With the purpose of identifying which method is the best one in teaching Ernest Hemingway's novels and its symbols, the researcher has conducted several experimental lessons, taken three progress tests and one final (post) test. In the middle of the experiment, the subjects were asked to answer a questionnaire which was developed by the researcher in order to identify opinions of the subjects about the classes they were having. Another reason of using a questionnaire was to find out the spheres that should have been developed to continue the research. The questionnaire consisted of five questions which asked the subjects about activities that they liked the most, what kind of method to learn English is effective for them, what sorts of activities they would like to have more during the classes.

Materials (activities and games) for experimental lessons were taken from the different books. For example: Most of them were taken from "Outline of American Literature" by Kathryn Van Spanckeren (1994), "Teaching Hemingway and War" by Alex Vernon (2016) and "Ernest Hemingway"(the critical heritage) by Jeffrey Meyers(2005). The theme which was taught is "Symbolism in Ernest Hemingway's writing". Games like "Jigsaw", "Puzzle", "", "" were used during the vocabulary lessons. Progress test and final test were all developed by the researcher.

The progress test was taken in order to identify the results of experimental lessons. Progress test was mostly based on the students' comprehension. According to the progress test Subjects had to do a role-play. Moreover, the test included a task which checked the ability of learners to comprehend.

The final (post) test was developed by the researcher. It was created to get the overall results that leads to final conclusion. Different test techniques were included in that post-test. Subjects had to take a card in which one of the novels was written and tell the main plot of the novel. Both progress and final tests were taken from Group1 (experimental) and Group 2 (traditional methods). All the test were considered to be reliable and valid. They had clear instructions, contained tasks that were unambiguous to the subjects and gave clear directions for scoring. The test were found out to be valid because they did not go out of the topics that were taught during the experimental lessons.

D. Data Collection and Analysis

The results and outcomes of the research substantially depends on the information the researcher dealt with and reviewed during collecting the data. This process is an essential part of the work as the paper is usually planned on the point of information acquired during the research. However, data collecting ways can be different depending on the research content, topic,

hypothesis and questions. Therefore, equally important to choose appropriate ways in accordance with the goals of the research.

Data collection of current research work was lead in the following sequence:

- ✓ Literature Review
- ✓ Observation
- ✓ Pre-Test
- ✓ Experiment
- ✓ Post-Test
- ✓ Assessment
- ✓ Feedback/discussion

Data collection is one of the key components of the research. Several factors can influence on the process of data collection. Thus, the researcher's goal was to find the effective ways of collecting reliable data. The researcher had an opportunity to discover and implement several methods of teaching Ernest Hemingway's novels and its symbols. The research was conducted between two same-level groups.

Before, during and after the experiment the researcher dealt with several ways of collecting data. They are to be outlined thoroughly in the following paragraphs:

➤ Literature Review.

Gathering relevant informations very first stage of data collection, more specifically, essential literature was an initial and basic part the research. In this connection, being familiar with views and observations of outstanding scholars and linguists is important to observe positive influence of teaching literature on learning English. Some viewpoints suggested by scholars helped to formulate the objectives:

- while teaching literature language background is required to understand deeply (Alex Vernon, 2016)

- Creativity and critical thinking together are aspects of "good" and purposeful thinking. Therefore, critical thinking and creativity can be considered as two sides of the same coin (Paul and Elder 2006).

- Critical thinking is associated with creativity, as it requires the ability to generate intellectual products

-Critical thinking is quite reconcilable with thinking "out-of-the-box", stimulating consensus and pursuing less popular approaches. People need critical thinking to evaluate and improve their creative ideas, therefore critical thinking is an essential part of creativity.

Furthermore, the literature review aided researcher to set not only objectives, but also research questions. For instance, which chosen methods can help improve students' critical thinking; in what degree can creative writing develop critical thinking; is creative writing the best tool to improve critical thinking and so on.

➤ Observation

The observation process lasted during a week and the researcher tried to be present as free listener in the English classes of four third year groups. This is completed to select suitable groups for the forthcoming research as well as to observe a course teacher. The researcher had a great chance to collect beneficial information concerning the study curriculum, classroom atmosphere, effectiveness of writing sessions and thinking abilities of the students during this stage.

➤ Pre-Test

The pre-test was designed and organized to get more specific data about students' preferences, level according to CEFR standards and their critical thinking degree. Before the test, they had discussion and

explanations on what critical thinking and creativity is. After brainstorming and discussing the questions, the researcher clarifies the notions, during the class students took the test consisting of 20 questions testing their critical thinking. The test consisted of five sections that make up the basic elements of critical thinking and students were given 30 minutes to fulfil the task. Moreover, the researcher asks students to write an argumentative essay on the topic from the book 501 WRITING PROMPTS a home task and provides with the rubrics to evaluate critical thinking. The researcher keeps the record of the results for further investigation.

The use of pre-test (Appendix I) aided the researcher to make a final conclusion of two groups that are to be designated to become the subjects of the experiment held during the research. The pre-test was the same for both 06-13 and 08-13 groups.

➤ Experiment

Teaching experiment is the next stage where researcher chooses one group to conduct lessons and teaches traditional pieces of writing rather than creative ones. Tasks contain traditional letter writing, report writing and summary writing which are considered as non-creative writing. Moreover, the students of the latter group were taught and practiced to write creative pieces of writing such as argumentative essays, short stories, scripts and diaries. The practical purpose of such dividing up was to compare two attitudes and try to illustrate advantageous aspects of teaching creative writing in improving critical thinking.

All lesson plans, rubrics, instruction papers and task formats were specially prepared and worked out deliberately to conduct the

research during classes. The researcher conducted 12 lessons to experiment subject, two lessons to make observations before the research started and two lessons to take pre- and post-tests.

Post-tests were taken from both groups at the end of the experiment. The group that was taught non-creative writing had a simple test format for writing, on the other hand the second experimental group was assessed according to creative writing task.

➤ Post-test

Different subjects of the experiment had different post-tests. Traditional group had non-creative writing task, while an experimental group was to write creative task.

➤ Assessment

Moreover, the analysis of the tests and their results was one of the most effective methods. It was completed in order to evaluate, compare and analyze the results of both different types of writing and their effect on students' critical thinking.

➤ Feedback

Receiving feedback from students was the last crucial point. As the main objective of the researcher was to gain positive effect in students' performance and critical thinking ability, the conducted experiment had a noticeable effect on the results.

IV. RESULTS

Palestinian teachers need to know many methods of teaching English literature in order to use them in teaching 'poetry, novel and drama'. Consequently, every method suits a specific situation, so it's the teachers' job to choose and change his methods according to the changeable situation. Keshta (2000: 36) mentioned some methods of teaching language and literature;

1. Communicative Language Teaching Approach

Communicative language teaching is the methodology which has perhaps most dominated classrooms in recent decades. The communicative movement has swept along almost everything and everyone in its path. There are excellent opportunities for English language teachers to create lively, attractive, interactive modern language lessons that maximize target-language use and make the culture of the language three dimensional.

Richards and Rodgers (2004:153) classifies the communicative approach as one of the most recent methods of language teaching. It began in Britain in the 1960s as a replacement to the earlier structural method, called Situational Language Teaching. As a result, that approach uses any activity that engages learners in authentic communication. It emphasizes interaction as both the means and the ultimate goal of learning a language.

2. Carter's three approaches

Carter (as cited in Keshta, 2000) identified three main approaches to teaching literature in EFL classes: (a) an information-based approach, (b) a personal-response-based approach, and (c) a language-based approach.

a. The information-based approach: tended to be teacher centered, relying almost exclusively on lecturing and printed materials, thus overvaluing information and undervaluing creative thinking. The lecturers spent most of the time speaking, arguing, citing eminent critic's points of view, balancing them, and timing the scale in favor of a certain view. Students were passive and did nothing except strive to

write down some fragmentary notes to memorize for examination purposes.

b. Personal-response-based approach: this approach focused on motivating the students to read by relating the themes and topics in the literary works to their personal experience. This approach was basically anti-analytic. It was closely related to a language model for reading literature in order to make the text one's own (Carter, 1991:61)

c. Language-based approach: this approach derived its impetus from the developments in the field of stylistics and text linguistics. Students were encouraged to read between the lines, rather than just for vocabulary in the lines of a text. It concentrated on 'process of reading' and was less concerned with literary text. In other words, it trained students to manipulate the possibilities of language, which was the guide to literary interpretation (Carter, 1991: 61).

3. A Storytelling Approach to Literature

Storytelling plays an important role in children's lives. Approaching the novel as one story to be told, shared and experienced over and over made the language learning experience much more collaborative. The children gradually reconstructed the general meaning and ideas along with their own feelings and existing knowledge. The teachers told or read the story dramatically, used the illustrations, played the story on tape and on film. The children took a much less analytic approach to text at this age. They used it to expand their imaginative and creative powers and play with the fun sound of words.

4. Process-based Teaching:

In process-based teaching, many strategies used in ESL teaching were directly applied

to the teaching of literature. Rewriting, prediction activities, and role playing were used in the literature lesson. Processbased teaching aimed to involve students with the text and develop their perceptions of it. The channel of communication between teacher and student was no longer exclusively one way. The instructor's aim was to encourage greater independent learning by using an interactive, communicative approach to enhance the content-area material. Examples of generally effective methods that could be employed by the English literature teacher were the creation of a learner-centered classroom, promotion of classroom interaction, cooperative learning, peer tutoring, an integrated skills approach and a process approach to writing. (Ervin, 1991- cited in Keshta , 2000: 37-38)

5. Representational Language-Learning Method:

A method current used in the ESL classroom was the representational language-learning approach:

A philosophy of language teaching which incorporates examples of text of any kind that demonstrate how language works within the rules and beyond the rules will expose learners to the representational possibilities of all language including the acquisition of a new awareness of their native language. (Carter and McRae, 1996: 20, cited in Keshta,2000)

6. Author-oriented approaches

Klarer (2003:90-91) explained that the author-oriented approach established a strong and direct link between the literary text and the biography of the author in which the facts, events, and dates in an author's life are juxtaposed with the literary elements of his or her work. Autobiographies are obviously suitable for

that approach. In many cases autobiographical material enters the fictional text. The American playwright Eugene O'Neil (1888-1953), for example, used veiled autobiographical elements in his play *Long Day's Journey into Night*. O'Neil used real people and dramatized events from his family life.

V. DISCUSSION

Literature was initially the main source of input for teaching in language classes in the era of Grammar Translation Method but since then it has been dropped down the pedestal. In fact with the advent of structuralism and audio-lingual method, literature was downplayed and ergo discarded to the periphery(Collie& Slater, 1987,p.2). Also in the era of CLT, literature was neglected and more attention was given to dialogues and conversations which were more practical and visible in the real world situation.

Nobody can deny the fact that most scholars agreed that teaching literature is a way of changing nations into better citizens. In Britain, literature's purpose was to moralize, civilize, and humanize. In the USA, after the civil war, literature was viewed as "a repository of morals and spiritual values. Teaching literature became an explicitly political act for radical and minority groups in university. Teaching literature became important not only in education but also in life. Habib (1994:5) considered the value of literature lying in the fact that it is an attempt to explore, recreate and seek for the meaning in human experience. Literary writers try to dramatize their insights by using language in a special way in order to embody their visions, contrast meaning and produce effects. Keshta (2000:23-24) touched the same point when he explained

that lectures and memorization, particularly, for the non-native English – speaking students, will neither help students discover the real meaning of the text, nor allow them to understand the author’s cultural context and intent. Therefore, teachers must seek ways to encourage young minds into creativity in a world full of passive entertainment. Teachers must develop lessons that can bring back the enthusiasm to understand the vague corners of the social and political life.

Value of Teaching Literature

Keshta (2000: 20) stated that Literature is a microcosm of an entire society, a little window that permits us to look into the cultural values, traditions, and lifestyles of people. As a person’s word reflects character, so does literature reflect the unique character of a group of people who share a language.

Ghosn (1998: 34) stated some benefits of literature:

- ✓ authentic literature provides a motivating, meaningful context for language learning, and it presents natural language at its finest, promoting vocabulary development in context;
- ✓ literature stimulates oral language and involves the child with the text while exposing him or her to some aspect of the target language culture;
- ✓ literature can promote academic literacy and critical thinking skills and has the potential of fostering private interpersonal and intercultural attitudes;
- ✓ good literature deals with some aspects of the human condition and attempts to come to some understanding of life.

Gray (2002: 1) mentioned five reasons commonly given for teaching literature for the upper-level learners :

1. Literature helps students understand and appreciate cultures and beliefs different from their own. "By constructing with the literary text a reality different from that of texts of information, students are given access to a world of attitudes, and values, collective imaginings and historical frames of reference that constitute the memory of a people or speech community. Thus literature and culture are inseparable" (Kramsch 1993: 175).
2. Literature is 'genuine' or 'authentic' material. Works of literature are usually not written for the specific purpose of teaching a language and are intended for native speakers. They can be an important supplement to other types of 'authentic' course materials like cartoons, city maps, timetables, and advertisements (Collie and Slater 1987: 4).
3. Literary texts can serve as an example of certain types of language patterns and structures (like vocabulary usage and syntax). Literature also "provides a rich context in which individual lexical or syntactical items are made more memorable. Reading a substantial and contextual body of text, students gain familiarity with many features of the written language – the formation and function of sentences, the varieties of possible structures, the different ways of connecting ideas...a literary text can serve as an excellent prompt for oral work (Collie and Slater 1987: 5).
4. It can provide personal enjoyment to students, establishing an emotional and aesthetic connection between readers and the text, and helping to contribute to

personal growth (Maley 2001: 181; McKay 1986: 193; Kramersch 1993: 177).

5. Selected texts, if interesting to students, can motivate them to read additional literature, thus increasing their reading proficiency (McKay 1986: 197; Krashen 2004: 54).

VI CONCLUSION

As a result of the above scientific research, we are based on the following conclusion:

1. There are many techniques and strategies used in that approach including jigsaw reading, matching, gap-filling, and reading aloud for teaching literature. The most important one is jigsaw reading. It is borrowed from language teaching. It is easy to prepare and comprises re-ordering of a text which has been scrambled. It may suggest some sort of games. It stimulates learner-learner interaction in the solving puzzles. It is known before asking questions, the teacher should give a model to keep the interaction going on. In this respect the term "jigsaw" is appropriate as it indicates a series of small increments which when added together will complete the picture.

2. In short, Symbols in Hemingway's stories differ from brilliance to the apparently minuscule. He fills his story with mixture of symbols that help the portray the whole matter of the story. Works of literature can lead us to see profoundly into and beyond things through the use of symbols which are generally actions, characters or even objects. The features of a symbol are connected to the abstractions it comprises. A thought connect to a field of worry in the work can be a symbol. The meaning and image of symbol express far more than mere words. Ernest Hemingway examines this by his effective use of symbolism in his works to search the disillusionment and the determination of individuals against the background of a pitiless environment.

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